

MECHANICAL BEHAVIORS OF MMC REINFORCED ALUMINUM ALLOY

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ABSTRACT

Mechanical behaviors of MMC(carbon fiber/Al) reinforced aluminum alloys have been investigated. The CF/Al fiber reinforced metal (FRM) was made by the squeeze casting method in a vacuum atmosphere. FRM specimen was placed at the center position of mold then cast with Al alloys together. The soundness of FRM/Al hybrid materials was examined by means of the ultra-sonic and X-ray techniques under non destructive manner. The defects or separation at FRM/Al interface was clearly detected. FRM/Al which had rigid interface deformed elastically until fracture of inside FRM. When FRM was fractured, the fracture strain was rapidly compensated by the surrounding plastically deformed Al alloy. These deformation behaviors were simulated using elastic-plastic analysis of finite element method (FEM). The comparison between experimental results and FEM calculations lead a quantitative understanding of mechanical properties of the MMC reinforced hybrid material.

INTRODUCTION

Metal matrix composite (MMC) have been studied extensively for many years aiming at light weight structural materials(1,2). Among different types of MMC, the fiber reinforced metal (FRM) have developed very rapidly in recent years, since high stiffness and high strength carbon or ceramic fibers are invented. CF/Al FRM is one of the promising materials and investigated extensively because of their excellent physical properties (3,4). FRM have a unique properties, which are high stiffness and strength in the fiber direction, while similar to matrix properties in the other direction. Because of fiber reinforced in particular direction, FRM have strong anisotropy in its stiffness and other physical properties. In order to utilize these FRM, careful considerations will be necessarily in the aspect of mechanics and structural design(5,6).

In the practical application of FRM, not only FRM itself use as a structural material, but FRM use as a reinforced element in the metal structure, for the purpose of strengthening the structure or partially improve physical properties of mechanical parts(7,8). In this research, FRM was placed in the center position of mold and cast with aluminum alloy. Then mechanical properties of FRM reinforced aluminum alloy(CF/Al hybrid material) was investigated.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Carbon fiber/Al FRM was made by squeeze casting method in a vacuum atmosphere. FRM specimen (4x10x100mm) was placed at the center position of mold, then molten aluminum alloy (Al-6.7wt%Si) casted into mold following solidified in air. As cast materials were examined by means of ultra-sonic and X-ray techniques under non-destructive manner. Mapping of both transmitted and reflected ultra-sonic sound can detect voids or other defects at the interface between FRM and Al. A X-ray technique also utilize to detect the feature of FRM in aluminum ingot and interface. Based on the results of these non destructive tests, FRM/Al hybrid specimens which have rigid interface were selected and cut into bending test pieces (12x12x75mm). The configuration of FRM/Al hybrid specimen is shown in Fig.1. Three-point bending tests were carried out under the following condition, span length 60mm, forcing jig whose radius was 2.5mm down to perpendicular of specimen with cross head speed 0.5 mm/min until specimen was fractured. Strain on the bottom surface of FRM/Al hybrid specimen was monitored by strain gauges during bending test. Fracture surface of FRM/Al hybrid specimen was observed by optical microscope.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Structure of hybrid material

The soundness of FRM/Al hybrid material is depend on the condition of casting. A typical cross sectional morphology of specimen which show rigid interface, is observed optical microscope. As shown in Fig.2, initially orthogonal FRM specimen edge change to curved shape during cast with molten aluminum. Furthermore, density of carbon fiber was lowered and carbon fibers slightly separate a part. These observations indicating that surface region of FRM was remelted and mixed with molten metal then solidified together. In Fig.2 the interface between FRM/Al is not clear and no observable defect on the interface. On the other hand, some specimen shows large separation at FRM/Al interface. The soundness of interface was clearly detected using ultra-sonic C-scan and X-ray. Several specimens were cut and examined the separation at interface when C-scan detected the irregularity on its scanning image.

2. Bending Test

In Fig.3 bending stress-deflection curves of FRM/Al hybrid specimen is shown with the same size of Al-Si specimen as a reference. Youngs modulus of hybrid specimen is increased due to the FRM reinforced element to compare with that of Al-Si specimen. FRM/Al hybrid material deforms elastically up to 200MPa and shows slight plastic deformation until 258MPa then abrupt stress drop occurs. After FRM was fractured, fracture strain was rapidly compensated by the plastic deformation of surrounding Al alloy. On the contrary to that, Al-Si specimen yield 120 MPa and plastically deformed with parabolic work hardening rate as shown in Fig.3. When the bending stress-deflection curve of hybrid specimen is compare with reference specimen, maximum stress of hybrid specimen have not been improved, however its yield stress appears twice higher than that of reference specimen. If we use this hybrid material as engineering structure, high stiffness and high yield stress would become great advantages. This reinforcing effect would be varied with arrangement or design of hybrid structure. Therefore, if we simulate the mechanical behavior of hybrid material using

finite element method (FEM), optimized structural design can be achieved by FEM simulation.

Fig.1 The configuration of FRM/Al hybrid specimen

Fig.2 A typical cross sectional structure of the hybrid specimen

Fig.3 Bending stress-deflection curves of FRM/Al hybrid and Al-Si specimens

3.FEM calculation

Fig.4 shows the finite element mesh model currently used for simulation of hybrid structure. Considering symmetry of hybrid bending bar, a quarter part of bar was examined. The model was consisted with three layers, in which one layer is CF/Al composite material and the other two layers are aluminum. In table I, material properties of CF/Al composite are listed. Those value was also calculated using Tsai-Uemura's equations (9,10). Apparently, this FRM has large anisotropy in its elastic properties, those are high stiffness in fiber direction and low stiffness in perpendicular to fiber directions. In

Table I Elastic coefficients of CF/Al composite (\checkmark calculated)

Youngs Modulus	E_{11}	239	GPa
	$E_{22}=E_{33}$	97.2	GPa
Poisson's Ratio	$\nu_{12}=\nu_{13}$	0.295	
	ν_{23}	0.321	
Shear Modulus	$G_{55}=G_{66}$	61.7	GPa
	G_{44}	27.8	GPa

Note: Matrix properties $E_m=73.1$ GPa $\nu=0.321$
 Fiber properties(11) $E_{f1}=350$ GPa $\nu=0.28$
 (l: fiber direction) $E_{ft}=121$ GPa $G_{flt}=137$ GPa
 (t: traverse direction)

this FEM calculation, not only elastic properties but plastic deformation was considered(12). The work hardening properties was provided by actual tensile tests of Al-Si alloy under tensile deformation. On the other hand, CF/Al composite show only little plastic deformation, so that it is accounted if the stress level is beyond the fracture stress of CF/Al FRM which was experimentally determined (≈ 420 MPa), FRM abruptly fractured.

Fig.5 demonstrate that load-displacement curves of FRM/Al hybrid bending bar and aluminum bar as a reference. Results of FEM simulation shown in Fig.5 can be compare with actual bending test results in Fig.3. Basically, very good agreements exist between FEM calculation and experiment in a qualitative manner. However, FEM calculation, in which it was presumed that the interface between FRM and aluminum is perfectly connected, shows larger reinforced effect than experiment of FRM/Al hybrid specimen. This result also suggest that importance of interface structure in the case of hybrid structure, on which forces should transfer through different material.

The stress distribution of σ_{xx} on the surface of hybrid structure is shown in Fig.6. On top surface, high intensity of compressive stress is existing, on the other hand, stress on the bottom surface that is hidden in Fig.6 shows tensile stress. On the side surface transition of tension to compression stresses is clearly observable. It is noticed that neutral line of hybrid specimen does not lie on the exact center line of specimen, which simple bending test with homogeneous material predicted. Furthermore, stress level is not uniform over the hybrid material, CF/Al FRM part shows much higher stress level than aluminum part of specimen, because high stiffness of FRM give the higher stress at the same elastic strain. After aluminum part of specimen yield, CF/Al FRM does not yield and still deform elastically until stress level reaches fracture stress of FRM.

4. Effects of hybrid structure

FRM/Al hybrid material in which FRM used as the reinforced material, demonstrates superiority in its mechanical behavior. Due to the high stiffness FRM used as the reinforced element, hybrid specimen shows higher stiffness than aluminum alone both experimentally and theoretically. If we change the volume fraction of FRM, the stiffness value of hybrid material is easily controlled in a range between stiffness coefficient of FRM and that of aluminum. Furthermore, reinforced FRM have higher strength than aluminum. This effect clearly seen in Figs.3 and 5, the yield stress of hybrid material is beyond 250 MPa, on the other hand Al-Si alloy shows 120 MPa. FEM calculation of FRM/Al

hybrid model provide detail stress strain informations of this model, assuming that interface between FRM and aluminum is perfectly connected. FEM calculation does not predict the deformation behavior of hybrid material after FRM fractured. However, bending experiment of FRM/Al hybrid material (Fig.3) shows specimen did not fracture completely, moreover, surrounding aluminum rapidly compensate the fracture strain of FRM. This observation indicate one of advantageous points of hybrid structure, a crack does not propagate rapidly even if reinforced FRM is fractured. In the practical use, this type of hybrid structure would not show sudden fatal fracture when reinforced FRM are broken.

Fig.4 The finite element model for FRM/Al hybrid structure

Fig.5 Calculated load displacements curves of FRM/Al hybrid structure and Al-Si model

Fig.6 Stress distribution contour lines of σ_{xx} on the surface of hybrid structure

SUMMARY

Mechanical behaviors of FRM/Al hybrid specimen was studied in both experiments and FEM simulation. Since high stiffness and strength CF/Al FRM was cast as a reinforce element, FRM/Al hybrid material show higher elastic modulus and higher yield stress to compare with aluminum specimen alone. These mechanical properties can be predicted using FEM elastic-plastic analysis. Another advantageous point of this hybrid material is fatal fracture of hybrid structure can be evaded since ductile aluminum rapidly compensate the fracture strain of FRM.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

Authors would like to express thanks to Dr.Imafuku and Mr.Ishida for contributions of early part of experiments and non destructive tests.

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